

The importance of conducting research on source studies and ancient manuscripts

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Abstract: The object of study of source studies is historical sources. There was almost no discussion of the object. As for the subject of study of science, some difficulties have arisen in science related to its definition. This article highlights the importance of researching ancient manuscripts.

Key words: Source studies, manuscript, old, research, method, efficiency.

Аннотация: Объектом источниковедения являются исторические источники. Обсуждения объекта почти не было. Что касается предмета изучения науки, то в науке возникли некоторые трудности, связанные с его определением. В этой статье подчеркивается важность исследования древних рукописей.

Ключевые слова: Источниковедение, рукопись, старина, исследование, метод, эффективность.

Etymology is a science related to culture in the broadest sense of the word, that is, to everything created by man. Then the historical source is considered as a cultural

phenomenon, that is, as an object of study of various humanities. Thus, thanks to source studies, the basis for the integration of disciplines and interdisciplinary research is created. Source studies has an interdisciplinary character, that is, it takes the place of one of the fundamental subjects in the training of a specialist in humanities. in the 20s. In the 20th century, the subject was considered to be the possibility of involving the source in scientific practice and knowledge (ie, what conclusions can be drawn based on the source).

In the 1930s, S. N. Valk (1887-1975) in the "Great Soviet Encyclopedia" formulated the concept of the subject — the general doctrine of the document. Valk was the first to use the term "general resource studies" and noted its difference from other disciplines through the concept of the subject of study.

In the 1960s, one of the important issues of many theoretical discussions became the question of defining the subject of source studies.

The formation of source studies as a scientific discipline began in the second quarter of the 18th century. associated with names such as V. N. Tatishchev, M. B. Lomonosov, G. F. Miller, A. L. Shlozer. But the transformation of source studies into an independent scientific discipline occurs in the last third of the 19th century, because only after that the object and subject of research is defined, the methodology is developed, and the conceptual apparatus is developed. The second half of the 18th century - the beginning of the 19th century. The tradition of looking at historical sources as an independent research object was founded. This was reflected in the efforts of scientists to develop the principles of a critical approach to the study of historical news and the publication of documents.

In order for the research to be successful, it is necessary to choose the right method. Methods of scientific knowledge are divided into general and special methods. To solve the special problems of science, it is necessary to use special methods. In addition to special methods, there are also general methods used throughout the research in all areas of science. General methods of scientific knowledge are divided into 3 groups:

- 1) empirical research methods (observation, comparison, measurement, experiment);
- 2) methods used in empirical and theoretical research (abstraction, analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, modeling, etc.);
- 3) methods used in theoretical research (from abstraction to precision, etc.). The methodological basis of interdisciplinary research is the generality of the object of social and humanitarian sciences, and their subjects are different. The object of social humanitarian science is man, and all aspects of human life are studied. At the same time, the fact that research methods are different is a unique feature of the subject of social and humanitarian sciences. Researchers cover this issue in different ways. For example, T. Shider stated that the methods of social sciences include all forms of involving people to determine the information necessary for scientific analysis. These are interviews, questionnaires, and all types of social process observation. The historian is engaged in "secondary analysis" because all the data he uses are "residues" of previous events³⁴. According to T. Papadopoulos, history uses diachronic analysis - synthesis and explanation of historical processes, and social sciences - synchronic analysis, functional analysis and analysis of relations

not related to time³⁵. Therefore, in the new and most recent era, historical knowledge has developed in close connection with other social sciences. The main reason for this was related to the specialization of my science about "spirit" and society. In the 19th century and at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries, a number of independent sciences (sociology, psychology, including history and social psychology, anthropology) emerged, which proved that they can study society, groups of people, and people using special approaches and methods. . The results of the studies of these sciences gave historians the opportunity to study people in depth as members of social and ethnic communities, representatives of a certain psychology and imagination. According to I.M. Saveleva and A.V. Poletayevlam, "permanent and continuous contacts with social and humanitarian sciences made it possible to penetrate into the zones closed to the science of history, to use new methods, to experiment with historical material. We can show structuralism, post-structuralism, post-modernism and management as such interdisciplinary paradigms.

Observation is a process of active cognition through human sensory organs. In order for observation to serve as a basis for theoretical and practical actions, it is necessary to provide information about the features of the subject and the event. To be an effective way of learning, observation must meet several requirements: 1) planned; 2) directed; 3) active; 4) systematic. The results of observation in social and humanitarian sciences largely depend on the personality of the observer, his knowledge, life views and other subjective factors. In these disciplines, simple (ordinary) observation (facts and events are recorded from the outside) and

participatory (inside) observation (in which the researcher joins a certain social environment, adapts to it and analyzes the phenomenon "from the inside") are distinguished. In psychology, there is a distinction between self-observation (introspection) and empathy (entering into the essential experiences of another person, striving to understand their inner world - feelings, thoughts, desires, etc.)⁴¹. Social experiments are increasingly developing, they help to implement new forms of rationalization of social organization and management of society. The object of a social experiment is a certain group of people, one of the direct participants of the experiment, and it is necessary to take into account the interests of the researcher, while the researcher is directly involved in the situation he is studying. In psychology, in order to determine how certain mental activity is formed, the subject of the experiment is placed in various experimental conditions and is offered to solve a certain problem. This approach is called a formative experiment in pedagogical psychology. Social experiments require the researcher to strictly adhere to ethical and legal norms and principles. Here (as in medicine) "do no harm!" principle is important. "Serving as a tool to enter the inner world of a person" (V.V. Ilin) is the main feature of social experimentation. Comparison is one of the most common ways of knowing. It is not for nothing that it is said that "everything is known by comparison". Comparison allows to determine the similarities and differences of objects and events. As a result of comparison, the commonality characteristic of two or more objects or the differences between them is determined. Identification is a step in the way of knowing the rules. In order for the comparison to be effective, it must meet 2 main requirements:

- 1) realities that have something in common should be compared;
- 2) important, basic aspects of objects should be studied.

Thus, similar or close events or processes are compared with each other in a certain period in certain regions or in the world. For example, it can be useful if we consider as an object the tax system that existed in the khanates of Bukhara, Khiva and Oo'kan in the Middle Ages. When this topic is researched, it is possible to study such issues as tax policy, tax collection mechanism, tax authorities, tax amount and the population's attitude to it in these khanates. In addition, topics are researched by comparing the cVgarishlam of a certain period. As an example, a comparative study of the changes in the above-mentioned issues during the khanate period and later is important in clarifying the issue. Also, data comparison can be seen as the main result. But obtaining primary data is not the main purpose of the comparison. The goal is to obtain information as a result of the processing of primary signals. To be more precise, it is to know the true historical data by comparing it with the primary data. In particular, when studying the history of different historical periods, information from several sources can be involved in research. For example, when studying the history of Turkestan at the end of the 19th - 20th centuries, researchers can get more accurate information by comparing the normative legal documents, reports written by various officials, correspondence, statistical data, periodical press materials, visual sources, historical works. can be 0 is a more accurate method of comparison. The quality of the measurement depends on the measuring instruments and the behavior of the researcher. This method is mainly used in exact sciences. Analysis is a method of conducting scientific research by dividing a subject into its

components. Synthesis consists of combining the parts obtained as a result of analysis into a whole. In it, the events are interconnected, studied as a whole, the obtained results are summarized and conclusions are drawn. In order to determine the signs of an object, to divide it into parts, it is necessary to know what these signs are and what elements should be divided into them. Therefore, the analysis can be carried out only when the researcher covers the subject as a whole, relying on the deductive method. Because induction means "separation". Induction and deduction must coincide. A complete acquisition of data allows not only a true and correct assessment of reality, but also to determine the factors that help and hinder its development. Sometimes the researcher's withdrawal during the analysis leads to the logical breakdown of the research. In many studies, the repeated use of words such as "it should be noted" and "it should be said about this" indicates a lack of logical thinking.

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